

A CODE TO ANALYSE THE STRUCTURAL-TECHNOLOGICAL DESIGN OF FILAMENT WOUND PRESSURE VESSELS

G. Di Vita¹, M. Marchetti², M.Nappi²

¹C.I.R.A. - Italian Center for Aerospace Research, Via Maiorise, 81043 Capua, Italy

²Aerospace Department - University "La Sapienza" of Rome, Via Eudossiana 16, 00184 Rome, Italy

SUMMARY: Usually the alignment of successive circuits for the winding of a closed end vessel is not guaranteed, even when the winding process is set up by use of simulation. Often the alignment is obtained realising an additional hoop winding on one of the polar bosses, or by trials, varying slightly winding angle, band width or mandrel dimensions until the accomplishment of the objective. In order to establish a strategy for the solution of this problem, the influence of the technological variables - winding angle, band width, mandrel dimensions - on the technological parameters - dwell angle, slippage tendency, fiber tangency at the polar boss - was first investigated. Then a computer software, named "AL", was developed in order to automatically select the technological variables, able to give the alignment of the fibers without any additional winding on the polar bosses. The reliability of the code was experimentally tested applying the automatic optimisation method to the design and the successive manufacture of a scaled motor case.

KEYWORDS: filament winding, close end pressure vessel, winding circuits alignment

INTRODUCTION

The aircraft and aerospace industries are continuously investigating high strength to weight material systems. Fiber reinforced composites have established their value in the aerospace industry because they efforts to improve high strength to weight ratio, high temperature capability, resistance to aerospace environments and processing capability. One of the areas in which the advantages of composite materials can be widely applied to obtain the best results is that of the pressure vessels for aerospace applications.

The use of *filament winding* process to fabricate composite structures has become one of the main techniques in the composite industry. For certain closed shape composite structures, such as pressure vessels, it is probably the only technique used in production.

The primary advantages of filament winding are: lower cost for large number of components, due to relatively low material costs and to manpower reduction; the highly repetitive nature of fiber placement; the automation of the process. Disadvantages are: technological problems, such as inability to wind reverse curvature, possibility of slippage and misalignment of winding trajectory; need for mandrel; poor external surface.

One of the most important aerospace application of the filament winding technology is the solid propellant rocket motor cases manufacture. A typical motor case consists of two

isotensoid wounded domes and a cylindrical section. The pressure vessel is connected via an adapter skirt and flange to the rocket or satellite structure. The igniter and the nozzle are fixed at the polar opening interface fittings. The fibers, impregnated with a resin system, are wound by a numerically controlled high precision winding machine on a mandrel. After curing of the vessel an elastomer interlayer is prepared at the transition zone of the cylindrical part to the adapter skirt. Subsequently to a second curing cycle, the adapter flanges are machined and the complete motor case is ready for acceptance testing.

Fig. 1 : Solid rocket motor case section

The filament wound pressure vessel manufacture needs an integrated design procedure, due to the difficulty to satisfy both the structural and technological requirements. In order to make an automatic solution to the structural-technological design, a software system, named "ARIANNA", has been developed at the Materials and Technologies Department of CIRA. The software system ARIANNA allows to predict and, if the case, solve the technological problems of filament winding, such as inability to wind along certain trajectories with a specific winding angle, possibility of slippage and misalignment of winding trajectories, in respect of the structural requirements [1]. The system core, that gives the solution of structural-technological design of filament wound pressure vessels, consists of the following set of subsystems:

1. The Winding Trajectory Analysis module (FW). It optimises steady winding trajectory and calculates the thickness and fibers orientation of the wound composite [2]. Input data, as the geometry of the structure, the lamination sequence, the winding angle at user's defined control sections, the computing accuracy parameters, etc., can be easily varied giving the opportunity to optimise the complete winding with simulations.
2. The NASTRAN interface module (BULK). It gives the *bulk data* (geometrical configuration, lamination sequence, etc.) for the structural analysis, that currently can be performed making use of the NASTRAN FEM code.
3. The Machine Motion Analysis module (EY). It allows the generation of the path of motion for winding machines having 2, 3 or 4 degrees of freedom.
4. The CNC interface module. It allows the generation of the numerical control part program.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The design of filament wound pressure vessels requires the following steps:

1. Preliminary design, realised using netting-analysis methods, with the aim to address the defined loads.
2. Material selection, dictated by both performance and environmental constraints.
3. Detailed stress analysis, obtained using the finite-element techniques.
4. Manufacturing reliability test, realised using a simulation code or winding proof.

The reliability test is a fundamental investigation to verify the manufacturing of the filament wound structure. Of course there is a remarkable difference between using a simulation code and a winding a proof. In case of abort of the proof, the manufacturing cost will increase considerably. Otherwise, the use of a consistent numerical simulation makes the proof useless and gives the possibility to adjust the design. This means that the designer needs a consistent simulation code, such as ARIANNA, to prevent a manufacture failure. A basis knowledge of technological problem is required to realise it.

A satisfactory technological design of filament wound pressure vessels needs to satisfy the following basic conditions:

1. filament stability during winding;
2. filament tangency at the polar boss;
3. winding trajectories alignment.

For this reason the two following technological parameters have been defined:

- the *slippage tendency*, whose value characterises the stability of winding [2].
- the *dwell angle*, that measures the angular distance between the axis of successive winding trajectories, and therefore the alignment of successive circuits, as shown in Fig. 4.

For the *filament tangency at the polar boss* the introduction of a new technological parameter is not necessary.

To optimise the technological parameters the designer could change mandrel geometry or lamination sequence, i.e. the value of technological variables. The winding trajectory will be optimised when the dwell angle reaches an optimal value $(dwell)_{opt}$:

$$(dwell)_{opt} = \frac{w}{R \cdot \cos \alpha} \quad (1)$$

This parameter depends on band width of roving and the internal radius of mandrel.

where w is the band width, R the internal radius and α the winding angle.

Fig. 2: Optimal dwell angle

The technological variables that can affect the technological parameters are:

- a) the *winding angle*, whose value modifies also the structural behaviour. The winding angle in the cylindrical section could be constant or variable. As shown in Fig. 3, two sections where the winding angle can be varied has been defined: one on the left basis and one on the right basis of the cylindrical section.
- b) the *polar boss radius*, whose value modifies both the mandrel geometry and the structural behaviour.
- c) the *internal radius* of the case, whose value modifies both the mandrel geometry and the structural behaviour.
- d) the *band width* of the roving (Fig. 3), whose value modifies neither structural behaviour nor mandrel geometry.

In order to set a strategy for the solution of the alignment problem, the influence of the technological variables on the technological parameters has to be investigated. This “knowledge basis” was obtained through a numerical simulation parameters analysis, using the FW module of ARIANNA. Two different geometry were taken into account:

1. a test mandrel (Fig. 3), whose geometry and lamination sequence are defined according to the current pressure vessel bibliography on the matter [3], [4].
2. an ASTM D2585 standard specimen mandrel (Fig. 4), whose geometry and lamination sequence are defined according to the standard norm [1].

The purpose of the simulations is to give an idea of parameters versus variables behaviour, i.e. the analytic law between the dwell angle and each of the variables. The results of the simulation performed [5] are shown in the graphs in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 3: Test mandrel winding simulation

Fig. 4: ASTM D 2585 standard specimen mandrel winding simulation

Graph 1: [dwell angle - dwell optimal] Vs $[\alpha(\text{left})-\alpha(\text{right})]$

Graph 2: [dwell angle - dwell optimal] Vs $[R_p/R_0(\text{left})]$

Graph 3: [max. slippage tendency] Vs $[\alpha(\text{left})-\alpha(\text{right})]$

Fig. 5 : Test mandrel winding parameters

Graph 4: [dwell angle - dwell optimal] Vs $[\alpha(\text{left})]$

Graph 5: [dwell angle - dwell optimal] Vs $[\alpha(\text{left})-\alpha(\text{right})]$

Graph 6: [max. slippage tendency] Vs $[\alpha(\text{left})]$

Fig. 6 : ASTM specimen winding analysis parameters analysis

From the graphs shown in Fig. 5 and in Fig. 6 the following considerations can be summarised:

- a. The dwell angle increases when increasing the winding angle values in the left and in the right cylindrical section.
- b. The dwell angle decreases when increasing the polar openings, the internal radius and the roving band width.
- c. The dwell angle decreases when increasing the winding angles and the polar bosses difference between left and right cylindrical sections.
- d. It is not possible to predict the slippage tendency variation law as a function of winding angle.

THE AUTOMATIC ALIGNMENT "AL" CODE

General Description

A specific code, named "AL", has been written in order to automatically solve the alignment problem. Making use of an iterative procedure this code is able to reduce the dwell angle modifying the values of the technological variables.

The code is based on a simple algorithm that change the technological variables, rearranges the input data set and run a new simulation with the FW module of the ARIANNA code. From the output results the new values of *dwell angle* and *slippage tendency* can be evaluated. The "AL" code reiterates the procedure until the convergence condition has been satisfied, in respect of filament stability and polar bosses tangency. The convergence condition is defined in terms of overlap tolerance, i.e. in percent of band width overlap (*ovp*) between the first and the second winding trajectory, as shown in Fig. 7.

$$overlap\ tolerance = \left(\frac{ovp}{w} \right) \cdot 100 \tag{2}$$

Fig. 7 Overlap definition for the convergence condition

Structure of the Code

As shown in the Fig. 8, the AL code algorithm provides to change the value of each variable, according to the knowledge basis and to the maximum allowable variation of the technological variables. The code is constituted by the following modules:

Knowledge Basis: with the aim to reach the convergence solution at the first step, the code performs two preliminary simulations and calculate the linear regression slope. The knowledge basis is updated step by step during the iterative procedure.

User's input: the user can define which of the variables are allowed to vary during the iterative process. The user can change both the mandrel geometry and the lamination sequence when the project is in the preliminary phase. Obviously, when the geometry is already defined and cannot be changed only the lamination sequence can be varied.

Variables change: the variables have been selected evaluating their influence on the lamination sequence and the mandrel geometry. There is a priority that guides the variables choice at each step. Initially the algorithm tries to change the winding law on the cylindrical part (move control section option). If the convergence condition is not satisfied, the algorithm provides to vary the lamination sequence, i.e. the band width of roving and the winding angle. Finally, the alignment can be determined changing the geometrical variables, i.e. the polar bosses radius and the internal radius.

Verify: at the end of each step the algorithm provides to verify the output of FW, i.e. the dwell angle, the slippage tendency and the filament trajectory co-ordinates.

AL starts a set of controls on this values. The controls are:

- *Slippage tendency and polar bosses tangency verification.* If slippage or no-tangency occurs, a special subroutine provides to search a satisfying solution, changing the technological variable and running again the FW module.
- *Convergence condition analysis.* When the overlap, measured in percent of band width, reaches the imposed tolerance limit, the user will be able to simulate the winding trajectory on the optimised mandrel with the optimised lamination sequence, and then to run the FEM analysis.

Fig. 8: the AL algorithm

SOME NUMERICAL RESULTS

A scaled mandrel, for the burst pressure proof of a motor case, named Zefiro and available at the BPD D&S production plant, has been used in order to test the AL code. The scale of the mandrel has been reduced by 1/5 compared to the size of the Zefiro motor case; the geometrical dimensions are the followings:

polar boss radiuses respectively at the ignitor and at the nozzle side: 41.6 and 90.3 mm.

internal radius at the cylindrical part: 188.3 mm.

length of the cylindrical part: 905.5 mm.

The lamination sequence is made of nine plies, five helix winding plies and four hoop winding plies. In the sequence shown in Fig. 9, the ply thickness is 0.125 mm and the band width is 2.5 mm. The pressure vessel has been manufactured with CFRP prepreg.

The “AL” code has been tested to optimise the four helix winding plies of filament wound structure. Each ply had 23° and 26° nominal winding angle at the left and at the right cylindrical section respectively. The dwell angles for each layer have been calculated. They are summarised in Table 1 and requires the technological optimisation of the manufacture design.

Table 1: Dwell angle for various plies before the automatic alignment

Ply number	α (left)	α (right)	Δ (dwell angle)
1	23°	26°	-21,05°
3	23°	26°	-28,08°
5	23°	26°	-31,98°
7	23°	26°	-41,09

Fig. 9: Graphical simulation of the first ply before the optimisation

An optimal pattern 5 (a band is aligned to another one after 5 circuits) has been found for the Zefiro mandrel. In this situation the dwell angle is defined as the angular distance between the axis of the first and the 6th winding trajectory. For the optimisation procedure it has been supposed to change only the lamination sequence, i.e. the winding angle, and to have an overlap tolerance less than 10%. Moreover the left and right winding angles have been changed by the same amount. The result of this calculations is a new lamination sequence, with a small difference of winding angle, as summarised in Table 2. In Fig. 10 the resulting winding simulation for the first ply is shown.

Table 2: Winding angles at two sections after the automatic alignment

Ply number	α (left)	α (right)	Overlap Tolerance
1	23,4258°	26,4258°	7,03 %
3	23,5361°	26,5361°	4,125%
5	23,5733°	26,5733°	0,363%
7	23,6281°	26,6281°	2,538%

Fig. 10: Graphical simulation of the first ply after the optimisation

The NASTRAN input file has been obtained using the BULK task of ARIANNA. It includes the geometry, the local stacking sequences, the boundary conditions (in terms of constrains and loads) and the material of the Zefiro motor case. A structural analysis, that simulates the burst test, has been performed and the tensional field on each layer evaluated. Therefore, using the EY Machine Motion Analysis module and the CNC interface module of ARIANNA, the

numerical parameters required to control the winding machine movements have been calculated. The pressure vessel has been manufactured and, finally, loaded with an internal pressure up to burst.

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The software has been tested, with positive results at the BPD D&S laboratories and plants in Colleferro (Rome). One phase of the winding process for the Zefiro scaled motor is shown in Fig. 11 and can be compared with the simulation in Fig. 10. The experimental results agreed perfectly with the simulations confirming the reliability of the software.

CONCLUSIONS

The problem of the optimal alignment of successive circuits during winding of a closed end pressure vessel was studied. A software code, named "AL", was developed in order to automatically select the technological variables able to give the alignment of the fibers without any additional winding on the polar bosses. The alignment can be accomplished varying slightly, from their nominal value, some of the technological variables, such as winding angles, band width or dimensions of the mandrel, within the limits that the user can select for the specific case under consideration. The reliability of the code was experimentally tested applying the automatic optimisation method to the design and the successive manufacture of a scaled motor case with tangency of the fiber at the polar boss, alignment of the winding circuits and absence of slippage.

Fig. 11: Manufacturing of the Zefiro scaled mandrel

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